

THE ESSENCE OF PRINCIPLES, METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES AND MECHANISMS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the essence of the principles, methodological approaches and mechanisms of preschool educational organization management is presented.

In this part of the thesis, we turn to the analysis of the fundamental principles, methodological approaches and management mechanisms that form the basis of the activities of the preschool educational organization. The essence of the principles of management is their ability to manage management activities, ensure consistency between organizational goals and strategic decisions. From this point of view, special attention is paid to the principles of flexibility, inclusiveness and innovation, which allow to adapt to the dynamically changing conditions of the external and internal environment of the preschool educational organization. Methodological approaches to the management of a preschool educational organization are based on complex and systematic methods that allow analysis, planning, organization, motivation and control within the framework of a single management process. Particular attention is paid to the development of the personal competence of leaders, their ability to self-study and self-development, which is important for the innovative development of the educational process.

Based on the conducted scientific analysis, we presented our author's definition of preschool education management.

Preschool education management is a set of tools and processes aimed at implementing management decisions. Preschool education management includes not only formal processes such as planning and control, but also informal aspects, including corporate culture, leadership styles, and communication strategies, which together form an effective system for managing a preschool education organization.

Management mechanisms in pre-school educational organizations include specific tools and procedures aimed at the implementation of management tasks. They cover a wide range of activities, from strategic planning and budgeting to quality control of educational services and staff development. Effective use of these mechanisms helps to optimize management, increase the efficiency of the educational process, and improve conditions for children's development.

Thus, the analysis of the nature of the principles, methodological approaches and mechanisms of preschool education organization management allows not only to better understand the theoretical foundations of management in the field of preschool education, but also to identify the most effective strategies and practices. development of personal competencies of principals, thereby ensuring the improvement of the quality of the entire management and educational process.

Special attention is paid to the analysis of the essence of principles, methodological approaches and management mechanisms within the framework of a comprehensive study of the mechanism of personal competence development of principals in the management of pre-school educational organizations. This aspect of the research affects the basic foundations on which the preschool education management system is built and determines the main parameters that affect the effectiveness of management and the quality of the educational process.

In this section of the thesis, we will consider the essence of management principles. Management mechanisms of a preschool educational organization are specific tools and processes aimed at the implementation of strategic and operational management goals. An important aspect is the integration of various management functions and processes into a single system, which allows the effective operation of the organization and the achievement of its goals. The principles of management of preschool educational organizations serve as a basis for the formation of the general strategy and tactics of management activities. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Structure of principles of management of preschool educational organizations.

The principle of systematicity implies considering the organization of preschool education as a single system in which all elements are interconnected and interact with each other. The principle of consistency lies in the construction of an effective management system in a preschool educational organization. This means accepting the organization as a whole system, in which all elements, be it pedagogues, students, methodical complex, administrative and economic staff, are interrelated and interact with each other. It requires the leader to be able to see the whole picture and coordinate the activities of different departments of the organization to achieve common goals.

The principle of integrity focuses on the need to consider all aspects of the organization's activities, from educational programs to the educational process and administrative tasks. The principle of integrity aims to comprehensively consider all aspects of the activity of a preschool educational organization. This includes not only educational programs and the learning process, but also management, financial planning, security, and creating a conducive learning environment. This approach helps to form a single development strategy of the organization that takes into account and harmoniously combines all the components of successful preschool education.

The principle of innovation emphasizes the desire to constantly update and improve methods and approaches in education and management. The principle of innovation emphasizes the importance of introducing new methods and approaches to continuous research and management. The pursuit of innovation not only helps to improve the quality of the educational process, but also ensures the adaptation of the preschool education organization to the changing conditions and needs of society. An innovative approach to management includes the introduction of modern educational technologies, the development and implementation of innovative child development programs, as well as the use of advanced methods of organizing management work.

REFERENCES:

1. Morozova Tatyana Petrovna. Pedagogicheskie osnovy upravleniya razvitiem doshkolnogo obrazovatel'nogo uchrejdeniya: Dis.kand. Ped. Nauk : 13.00.07 : Rostov n/D, 2002 216 c. RGB OD, 61:03-13/180-6
2. Angela Nikolaevna Morozova. Upravlenie methodicheskoy rabotoy v doshkolnom obrazovatel'nom uchrejdenii na diagnosticheskoy osnove: Dis. ... candy. ped. Nauk : 13.00.07 : Moscow, 2000 244 c. RGB OD, 61:01-13/1012-5